

I.FAST

Innovation Fostering in Accelerator Science and Technology

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MILESTONE REPORT

CONSTRUCTION AND RF TESTS OF THE COMPACTLIGHT ACCELERATING STRUCTURE PROTOTYPE

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ABSTRACT

This milestone (MS30) confirms the successful construction of the CompactLight accelerating structure prototype within the I.FAST WP7. This achievement marks a key step towards Deliverable D7.6 and the realization of the full accelerating structure.

IFAST Consortium, 2025

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Delivery Slip

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1. Introduction

This report describes the X-band accelerating structure and the RF tests for the CompactLight project (<https://www.compactlight.eu/>). The detailed construction phases of the first prototype of the structure are reported in the D7.5, hereinafter the CERN metrology report are analyzed together with the RF tests.

CompactLight was a Design Study funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme, completed in 2021 with the design of an innovative, compact, and cost-effective hard X-ray FEL facility, using the most advanced technologies developed for accelerator components, in terms of high brightness photo-injectors, compact and very high-gradient X-band accelerating structures, as well as state-of-the-art undulators.

The CompactLight linac consists of approximately one hundred 0.9m long X-band accelerating structures that can operate both in a high-gradient mode, at 65 MV/m and 100 Hz pulse repetition rate, and high-repetition rate mode, at 30 MV/m and 1 kHz pulse repetition rate. The structure parameters have been optimized for both radio frequency and beam dynamics performance and have higher order transverse mode suppression for stable two-bunch operation. The cooling circuit has been designed to accommodate the high average power of the high-repetition rate mode and optimized for minimum difference between operating modes. Finally, the mechanical design of the structures has also been analyzed and optimized for industrial production.

2. The CompactLight accelerating structure

The design and optimization of a linear accelerator based on traveling-wave structures involve several critical steps [1] and the design process typically involves several iterations among them to achieve an optimal balance between performance, efficiency, and reliability. These processes are detailed reported in the D7.5.

With the average iris radius of the structure defined, the first step in designing the entire structure was to identify the optimal lengths for both Constant Impedance (CI) and Constant Gradient (CG) structures.

The effective shunt impedance, as a function of the accelerating structure attenuation, is shown in Fig. 1a for both CI and CG structures, while the optimal structure length as a function of the average iris aperture is depicted in Fig. 1b. For the CI structure, the optimal length has been fixed at 0.890 m, and for the CG structure, 0.818 m. These values have been used as the basis for a numerical optimization of iris tapering.

Two-bunch operations in CompactLight is essential for pump-and-probe experiments. However, this operational mode introduces a critical design challenge: addressing the long-range transverse wakefield behavior of the accelerating structure. The wakefield excited by the leading bunch can influence the trajectory of the trailing bunch, leading to emittance growth. To mitigate this, long-range transverse wakefield suppression is necessary. This suppression can be achieved by varying the iris diameter along the structure's length, which detunes the synchronous frequencies of the most significant transverse modes. This detuning induces decoherence in the transverse wakefield, reducing its amplitude.

Figure 1: (a) : Effective shunt impedance as a function of the section attenuation for CI and CG structures ,
(b) Optimal structure length as function of the average iris radius for CI and CG structures.

Through a multi-parameter optimization of the tapering parameters, the final iris aperture and thickness profiles were determined, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The blue line represents the dimensions of the linear iris design, while the red line shows the Gaussian-like design.

Magnetically coupled input and output power couplers were chosen for their compact design. Key design considerations for these couplers include achieving impedance matching, minimizing peak surface electric fields, and reducing the quadrupolar component of the accelerating field within the structure.

Figure 2: The iris dimension of the RF structure. Left figure is the distribution of the iris aperture.
Right figure is the distribution of the iris thickness.

At the end of optimizations the Table 1 lists the main parameters of the structures that can operate both in a high-gradient mode, at 65 MV/m and 100 Hz pulse repetition rate, and high-repetition rate mode, at 30 MV/m and 1 kHz pulse repetition rate.and the RF module.

Table 1: Main parameters of the RF structures and modules

Parameter	Units	Value		
Frequency	GHz	11.994		
Peak Klystron power (100-250 Hz)	MW	50		
Peak klystron power (1kHz)	MW	10		
RF pulse length (250 Hz)	μs	1.5 (0.15)		
Waveguide power attenuation	%	≈ 10		
Average iris radius $\langle a \rangle$	mm	3.5		
Iris radius a	mm	4.3-2.7		
Iris thickness t	mm	2-2.24		
Structure length L_s	m	0.9		
Unloaded SLED Q-factor Q_0		18000		
External SLED Q-factor Q_{ext}		23300		
Shunt impedance R	$M\Omega/m$	85-111		
Peak modified Poynting vector	$W/\mu m^2$	3.4		
Group velocity v_g/c	%	4.7-0.9		
Filling time t_f	ns	146		
Repetition rate	Hz	100	250	10000
Pulse compressor		ON	OFF	ON
Required klystron power	MW	44	44	9
Average accelerating gradient	MV/m	65	30	30

The gradient profile along the structure (after one filling time) is shown in Fig. 3, while the power distribution (averaged over the pulse length and normalized to the peak value) is illustrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Accelerating gradient profile along the structure after one filling time.

Figure 4: Power distribution (averaged over the pulse length and normalized to the peak value).

3. First accelerating structure stack assembly

The following pictures show the partially constructed accelerating structure at the CPI TMD factory (detailed construction process is reported in D7.5).

The whole structure, was brazed mid of February 2025. Figure 5 shows the entire structure assembled before brazing.

Figure 5. Entire structure before brazing

Prior to running this braze, a test furnace run was performed to ensure that the braze profile chosen would reach the desired brazing temperature. A thermocouple was attached to the centre of the test mass and the results showed that the braze profile was adequate.

Following the braze run, the structure was removed from the furnace and placed into CPI TMD's cleanroom for vacuum leak testing, see Figure 6. The structure was tested using ultra-high vacuum leak checking equipment and was unfortunately shown to have a gross leak.

Figure 6. RF structure after brazing

CPI TMD attempted to pinpoint the source of the leak, but the structure appeared to be leaking from several sources, and the size of the leak was too large to be able to accurately identify the sources.

In addition, mechanical damage was noted on the outside of the RF coupler, probably due to the thermal expansion of the structure into its braze jig during the brazing cycle.

Prior to furnace, CPI TMD had put the brazing jig through a wet hydrogen greening process, which forms a green oxide layer on the stainless steel. This green oxide layer is applied to prevent the brazing parts from sticking to the braze jig. In addition to this, the braze jig was loosened once the structure was positioned in the furnace, to allow room for thermal expansion of the copper structure.

Despite this, copper did stick to the stainless steel braze jig and expanded into it, causing damage to at least the outside of the stack.

Following preliminary tests at CPI TMD, at the beginning of April 2025 the structure has been sent to CERN for low level RF measurements, mechanical tests (to assess any damage on the RF couplers) and for further evaluation to identify the cause of the vacuum leaks.

In particular CERN Metrology will check the alignment of the structure and, using an endoscope, will also check the brazing alloy penetration on the beam axis of the structure.

In addition, in order to identify the sources of vacuum leaks, the vent holes of the brazing channel will be sealed.

Finally, if necessary, to fully understand the cause of the vacuum leaks, the section will be cut and the brazed areas are analysed.

4. Metrology and vacuum tests

Below the metrology report carried out at CERN to verify the alignment of the structure (the full report is in Annex 1).

		MÉTROLOGIE EN-MME-MM RAPPORT DE CONTRÔLE	
EDMS	3317020	Date de la mesure	03/07/2025 15:53
Job	3101080	N° de plan	134-75071
Client	GONZALEZ Sergio	Désignation	IFAST XBAND ASSY
Contrôleur	DEQUIDT Mike	Fournisseur	
Machine	ZEISS Prismo Ultra 12-18-10	N° de pièce	135-00882-002-2
Précision des mesures	1,2 µm + L/500mm	Valeurs rouges	● 203
Température	20°C ±1°C		

Figure 7a, shows the structure under measurement with the reference axes.

Measurements taken:

1. The diameters of all the cells in the structure (102 in total), evaluating their deviations from the nominal values. Fig. 7b shows the measured values for the first 10 cells.
2. The value of a reference location for each cell in the structure (102 in total), evaluating all deviations from the nominal values. Fig. 7c shows the measured values for the first 10 cells.
3. The structure axe, assessing any deviations in X^+ , X^- , Y^+ , Y^- , see Fig. 8

All the values shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8 are in mm.

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
Ø Diamètre1(1)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
Ø Diamètre1(2)	80,0120	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0120	0,0100
Ø Diamètre1(3)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
Ø Diamètre1(4)	80,0112	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0112	0,0092
Ø Diamètre1(5)	80,0092	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0092	0,0072
Ø Diamètre1(6)	80,0113	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0113	0,0093
Ø Diamètre1(7)	80,0146	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0146	0,0126
Ø Diamètre1(8)	80,0125	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0125	0,0105
Ø Diamètre1(9)	80,0093	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0093	0,0073
Ø Diamètre1(10)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080

b)

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
⊕ Localisation1(1)	0,0302	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0302	
⊕ Localisation1(2)	0,0219	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0219	
⊕ Localisation1(3)	0,0647	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0647	0,0147
⊕ Localisation1(4)	0,0888	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0888	0,0388
⊕ Localisation1(5)	0,1152	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1152	0,0652
⊕ Localisation1(6)	0,1377	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1377	0,0877
⊕ Localisation1(7)	0,1589	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1589	0,1089
⊕ Localisation1(8)	0,1807	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1807	0,1307
⊕ Localisation1(9)	0,2010	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2010	0,1510
⊕ Localisation1(1C)	0,2172	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2172	0,1672

c)

Figure 7. a) Accelerating structure with coordinate system under measurement
 b) Measurement of the diameter of the first ten cells of the structure
 c) Reference point measurements of the first ten cells of the structure

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
— Rectitude axe cylindre	0,5177	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,5177	0,4177
— Rectitude Y-	0,1301	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,1301	0,0301
— Rectitude X-	0,5001	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,5001	0,4001
— Rectitude X+	0,4842	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,4842	0,3842
— Rectitude Y+	0,0350	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,0350	

Figure 8. Structure axis measurements (on the left) and X⁺, X⁻, Y⁺, Y⁻ deviations (table on the right)

Summarizing 203 measurement points are out of tolerance, with deviations of up to 1.25 mm. The axis of the structure has a clear “banana shape”, with a maximum deviation in the middle of up to 0.42 mm, almost 100 times higher than expected, that make the structure use rather problematic!

We are analysing the issues that led to these unacceptable results. These are probably due to the method used to assembly the whole cell stack, the structure rotation before brazing, or an inadequate compensation for copper expansion during brazing. As already reported, the copper stick to the stainless steel braze jig and expanded into it during brazing.

All these issues will need to be addressed and corrected before the assembling and brazing of the second structure.

5. Low level RF measurements and RF characterization

Following the mechanical measurements, the structure was measured and characterized on a microwave bench (see Fig. 9 below).

Figure 9. Structure RF measurements

A 110 GHz, continuous sweep, Rodhe & Schwarz vector network analyzer (VNA), with a four-port calibration, has been used, using the following configuration:

- Center frequency 11.994 GHz
- 300 MHz span
- No. of points 10001
- IF bandwidth 1kHz

The structure was characterised by measuring the S parameters in reflection (S_{11} , S_{22}), see Fig. 10, and transmission (S_{12} , S_{21}), see Fig. 11, representing the magnitude and phase of RF reflected and transmitted. The values shown in the graphs include the air correction.

Figure 10. Structure input and output S parameters (in reflection)

Figure 11. Structure input and output S parameters (in transmission)

The measured parameters are quite acceptable. Although the structure has a slightly high insertion loss, (≈ 10 dB), it is quite well matched with a return loss > 20 dB.

At this stage, it was not possible to perform the bead-pull test, to measure the electric field distribution within the accelerating structure, as its overall length, including the input-output RF couplers, exceeds one metre and the available bead-pull system was limited to one. We plan to modify the system and repeat the RF tests, including the RF field distribution.

6. Conclusions

The first part of the project for the construction of the CompactLight accelerating structure has been completed. The pre-prototype was built in several stages. While some stages went smoothly, without particular problems, others encountered severe technical issues.

In particular:

- We have not experienced any particular problems with the RF design and the development of the engineering drawings of the structure.
- The precision machining of all the elementary cells were successful.
- Most of the brazing tests, carried out on a reduced number of cells (3-5), went well.

Conversely, the activities that proved to be somewhat problematic were:

- The stacking of cells and assembly of the entire structure, as well as the braze jig, used for secure rotation and lifting of the fully assembled structure prior to brazing, proved to be quite problematic.
- The brazing process, the instability of the oven temperature, and the inadequate compensation for copper expansion inside the jig during the brazing cycle, have all been problematic and have certainly contributed to the mechanical and vacuum issues encountered with the brazed structure.

For these reasons, it is crucial to identify the causes of the problems encountered in order to make the necessary changes to the brazing process for the second accelerating structure.

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8. Annex 1

ANNEXE 1

CERN METROLOGY REPORT

**MÉTROLOGIE EN-MME-MM
RAPPORT DE CONTRÔLE**

EDMS	3317020	Date de la mesure	03/07/2025 15:53
Job	3101080	N° de plan	134-75071
Client	GONZALEZ Sergio	Désignation	IFAST XBAND ASSY
Contrôleur	DEQUIDT Mike	Fournisseur	
Machine	ZEISS Prismo Ultra 12-18-10	N° de pièce	135-00882-002-2
Précision des mesures	1,2 µm + L/500mm	Valeurs rouges	● 203
Température	20°C ±1°C		

Commentaire

Nom du programme EDMS.3317020 - J3101080 - IAFST XBAND ASSY

Numero de serie

EDMS 3317020
 N° de plan 134-75071
 Désignation IFAST XBAND ASSY
 N° de pièce 135-00882-002-2
 Date/Heure 03/07/2025 15:53

Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
∅ Diamètre1(1)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(2)	80,0120	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0120	0,0100
∅ Diamètre1(3)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(4)	80,0112	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0112	0,0092
∅ Diamètre1(5)	80,0092	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0092	0,0072
∅ Diamètre1(6)	80,0113	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0113	0,0093
∅ Diamètre1(7)	80,0146	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0146	0,0126
∅ Diamètre1(8)	80,0125	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0125	0,0105
∅ Diamètre1(9)	80,0093	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0093	0,0073
∅ Diamètre1(10)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080
∅ Diamètre1(11)	80,0102	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0102	0,0082
∅ Diamètre1(12)	80,0123	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0123	0,0103
∅ Diamètre1(13)	80,0114	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0114	0,0094
∅ Diamètre1(14)	80,0116	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0116	0,0096
∅ Diamètre1(15)	80,0133	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0133	0,0113
∅ Diamètre1(16)	80,0143	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0143	0,0123
∅ Diamètre1(17)	80,0142	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0142	0,0122
∅ Diamètre1(18)	80,0158	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0158	0,0138
∅ Diamètre1(19)	80,0140	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0140	0,0120
∅ Diamètre1(20)	80,0118	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0118	0,0098
∅ Diamètre1(21)	80,0137	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0137	0,0117
∅ Diamètre1(22)	80,0154	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0154	0,0134
∅ Diamètre1(23)	80,0145	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0145	0,0125
∅ Diamètre1(24)	80,0136	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0136	0,0116
∅ Diamètre1(25)	80,0130	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0130	0,0110
∅ Diamètre1(26)	80,0118	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0118	0,0098
∅ Diamètre1(27)	80,0075	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0075	0,0055
∅ Diamètre1(28)	80,0089	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0089	0,0069
∅ Diamètre1(29)	80,0107	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0107	0,0087
∅ Diamètre1(30)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
∅ Diamètre1(31)	80,0098	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0098	0,0078
∅ Diamètre1(32)	80,0124	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0124	0,0104
∅ Diamètre1(33)	80,0124	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0124	0,0104
∅ Diamètre1(34)	80,0129	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0129	0,0109
∅ Diamètre1(35)	80,0129	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0129	0,0109
∅ Diamètre1(36)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128	0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(37)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(38)	80,0107	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0107	0,0087
∅ Diamètre1(39)	80,0110	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0110	0,0090
∅ Diamètre1(40)	80,0095	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0095	0,0075
∅ Diamètre1(41)	80,0135	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0135	0,0115
∅ Diamètre1(42)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128	0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(43)	80,0133	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0133	0,0113
∅ Diamètre1(44)	80,0113	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0113	0,0093
∅ Diamètre1(45)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128	0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(46)	80,0111	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0111	0,0091
∅ Diamètre1(47)	80,0131	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0131	0,0111
∅ Diamètre1(48)	80,0154	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0154	0,0134
∅ Diamètre1(49)	80,0121	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0121	0,0101
∅ Diamètre1(50)	80,0107	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0107	0,0087
∅ Diamètre1(51)	80,0127	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0127	0,0107
∅ Diamètre1(52)	80,0147	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0147	0,0127
∅ Diamètre1(53)	80,0176	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0176	0,0156
∅ Diamètre1(54)	80,0168	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0168	0,0148
∅ Diamètre1(55)	80,0126	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0126	0,0106
∅ Diamètre1(56)	80,0121	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0121	0,0101
∅ Diamètre1(57)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087	0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(58)	80,0092	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0092	0,0072
∅ Diamètre1(59)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080
∅ Diamètre1(60)	80,0079	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0079	0,0059

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
∅ Diamètre1(61)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087	0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(62)	80,0099	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0099	0,0079
∅ Diamètre1(63)	80,0074	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0074	0,0054
∅ Diamètre1(64)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087	0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(65)	80,0089	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0089	0,0069
∅ Diamètre1(66)	80,0094	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0094	0,0074
∅ Diamètre1(67)	80,0129	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0129	0,0109
∅ Diamètre1(68)	80,0166	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0166	0,0146
∅ Diamètre1(69)	80,0158	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0158	0,0138
∅ Diamètre1(70)	80,0118	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0118	0,0098
∅ Diamètre1(71)	80,0096	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0096	0,0076
∅ Diamètre1(72)	80,0091	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0091	0,0071
∅ Diamètre1(73)	80,0088	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0088	0,0068
∅ Diamètre1(74)	80,0069	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0069	0,0049
∅ Diamètre1(75)	80,0078	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0078	0,0058
∅ Diamètre1(76)	80,0081	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0081	0,0061
∅ Diamètre1(77)	80,0097	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0097	0,0077
∅ Diamètre1(78)	80,0115	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0115	0,0095
∅ Diamètre1(79)	80,0130	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0130	0,0110
∅ Diamètre1(80)	80,0103	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0103	0,0083
∅ Diamètre1(81)	80,0075	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0075	0,0055
∅ Diamètre1(82)	80,0072	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0072	0,0052
∅ Diamètre1(83)	80,0098	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0098	0,0078
∅ Diamètre1(84)	80,0088	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0088	0,0068
∅ Diamètre1(85)	80,0073	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0073	0,0053
∅ Diamètre1(86)	80,0096	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0096	0,0076
∅ Diamètre1(87)	80,0124	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0124	0,0104
∅ Diamètre1(88)	80,0120	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0120	0,0100
∅ Diamètre1(89)	80,0103	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0103	0,0083
∅ Diamètre1(90)	80,0131	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0131	0,0111

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
∅ Diamètre1(91)	80,0154	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0154	0,0134
∅ Diamètre1(92)	80,0161	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0161	0,0141
∅ Diamètre1(93)	80,0157	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0157	0,0137
∅ Diamètre1(94)	80,0128	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0128	0,0108
∅ Diamètre1(95)	80,0109	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0109	0,0089
∅ Diamètre1(96)	80,0122	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0122	0,0102
∅ Diamètre1(97)	80,0140	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0140	0,0120
∅ Diamètre1(98)	80,0087	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0087	0,0067
∅ Diamètre1(99)	80,0070	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0070	0,0050
∅ Diamètre1(100)	80,0074	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0074	0,0054
∅ Diamètre1(101)	80,0066	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0066	0,0046
∅ Diamètre1(102)	80,0100	80,0000	0,0020	-0,0020	0,0100	0,0080
⊕ Localisation1(1)	0,0302	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0302	0,0302
⊕ Localisation1(2)	0,0219	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0219	0,0219
⊕ Localisation1(3)	0,0647	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0647	0,0147
⊕ Localisation1(4)	0,0888	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0888	0,0388
⊕ Localisation1(5)	0,1152	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1152	0,0652
⊕ Localisation1(6)	0,1377	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1377	0,0877
⊕ Localisation1(7)	0,1589	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1589	0,1089
⊕ Localisation1(8)	0,1807	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1807	0,1307
⊕ Localisation1(9)	0,2010	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2010	0,1510
⊕ Localisation1(10)	0,2172	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2172	0,1672
⊕ Localisation1(11)	0,2351	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2351	0,1851
⊕ Localisation1(12)	0,2530	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2530	0,2030
⊕ Localisation1(13)	0,2692	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2692	0,2192
⊕ Localisation1(14)	0,2849	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2849	0,2349
⊕ Localisation1(15)	0,2971	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2971	0,2471
⊕ Localisation1(16)	0,3104	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3104	0,2604
⊕ Localisation1(17)	0,3235	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3235	0,2735
⊕ Localisation1(18)	0,3352	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3352	0,2852

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
⊕ Localisation1(19)	0,3479	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3479	0,2979
⊕ Localisation1(20)	0,3572	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3572	0,3072
⊕ Localisation1(21)	0,3664	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3664	0,3164
⊕ Localisation1(22)	0,3752	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3752	0,3252
⊕ Localisation1(23)	0,3838	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3838	0,3338
⊕ Localisation1(24)	0,3906	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3906	0,3406
⊕ Localisation1(25)	0,3969	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3969	0,3469
⊕ Localisation1(26)	0,4028	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4028	0,3528
⊕ Localisation1(27)	0,4081	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4081	0,3581
⊕ Localisation1(28)	0,4111	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4111	0,3611
⊕ Localisation1(29)	0,4138	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4138	0,3638
⊕ Localisation1(30)	0,4171	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4171	0,3671
⊕ Localisation1(31)	0,4191	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4191	0,3691
⊕ Localisation1(32)	0,4201	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4201	0,3701
⊕ Localisation1(33)	0,4196	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4196	0,3696
⊕ Localisation1(34)	0,4187	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4187	0,3687
⊕ Localisation1(35)	0,4161	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4161	0,3661
⊕ Localisation1(36)	0,4147	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4147	0,3647
⊕ Localisation1(37)	0,4111	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4111	0,3611
⊕ Localisation1(38)	0,4087	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4087	0,3587
⊕ Localisation1(39)	0,4040	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4040	0,3540
⊕ Localisation1(40)	0,3997	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3997	0,3497
⊕ Localisation1(41)	0,3908	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3908	0,3408
⊕ Localisation1(42)	0,3843	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3843	0,3343
⊕ Localisation1(43)	0,3753	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3753	0,3253
⊕ Localisation1(44)	0,3667	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3667	0,3167
⊕ Localisation1(45)	0,3564	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3564	0,3064
⊕ Localisation1(46)	0,3460	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3460	0,2960
⊕ Localisation1(47)	0,3343	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3343	0,2843
⊕ Localisation1(48)	0,3193	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3193	0,2693

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-	
⊕ Localisation1(49)	0,3065	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3065		0,2565
⊕ Localisation1(50)	0,2931	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2931		0,2431
⊕ Localisation1(51)	0,2779	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2779		0,2279
⊕ Localisation1(52)	0,2603	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2603		0,2103
⊕ Localisation1(53)	0,2428	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2428		0,1928
⊕ Localisation1(54)	0,2234	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2234		0,1734
⊕ Localisation1(55)	0,2048	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2048		0,1548
⊕ Localisation1(56)	0,1851	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1851		0,1351
⊕ Localisation1(57)	0,1657	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1657		0,1157
⊕ Localisation1(58)	0,1439	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1439		0,0939
⊕ Localisation1(59)	0,1215	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1215		0,0715
⊕ Localisation1(60)	0,0992	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0992		0,0492
⊕ Localisation1(61)	0,0765	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0765		0,0265
⊕ Localisation1(62)	0,0514	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0514		0,0014
⊕ Localisation1(63)	0,0259	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0259		
⊕ Localisation1(64)	0,0129	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0129		
⊕ Localisation1(65)	0,0391	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0391		
⊕ Localisation1(66)	0,0673	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0673		0,0173
⊕ Localisation1(67)	0,0970	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,0970		0,0470
⊕ Localisation1(68)	0,1284	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1284		0,0784
⊕ Localisation1(69)	0,1563	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1563		0,1063
⊕ Localisation1(70)	0,1871	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,1871		0,1371
⊕ Localisation1(71)	0,2188	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2188		0,1688
⊕ Localisation1(72)	0,2510	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2510		0,2010
⊕ Localisation1(73)	0,2833	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,2833		0,2333
⊕ Localisation1(74)	0,3164	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3164		0,2664
⊕ Localisation1(75)	0,3512	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3512		0,3012
⊕ Localisation1(76)	0,3854	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,3854		0,3354
⊕ Localisation1(77)	0,4227	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4227		0,3727
⊕ Localisation1(78)	0,4589	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4589		0,4089

**CONSTRUCTION AND RF TESTS OF THE COMPACTLIGHT
ACCELERATING STRUCTURE PROTOTYPE**

Milestone: MS30

Date: 22/09/2025

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Nom	Valeur mesurée	Valeur nominale	Dimension supérieure	Dimension inférieure	Deviation	+/-
⊕ Localisation1(79)	0,4954	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,4954	0,4454
⊕ Localisation1(80)	0,5319	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,5319	0,4819
⊕ Localisation1(81)	0,5722	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,5722	0,5222
⊕ Localisation1(82)	0,6098	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,6098	0,5598
⊕ Localisation1(83)	0,6495	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,6495	0,5995
⊕ Localisation1(84)	0,6894	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,6894	0,6394
⊕ Localisation1(85)	0,7329	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,7329	0,6829
⊕ Localisation1(86)	0,7754	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,7754	0,7254
⊕ Localisation1(87)	0,8185	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,8185	0,7685
⊕ Localisation1(88)	0,8604	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,8604	0,8104
⊕ Localisation1(89)	0,9037	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,9037	0,8537
⊕ Localisation1(90)	0,9489	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,9489	0,8989
⊕ Localisation1(91)	0,9957	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	0,9957	0,9457
⊕ Localisation1(92)	1,0416	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,0416	0,9916
⊕ Localisation1(93)	1,0865	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,0865	1,0365
⊕ Localisation1(94)	1,1334	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,1334	1,0834
⊕ Localisation1(95)	1,1809	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,1809	1,1309
⊕ Localisation1(96)	1,2272	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2272	1,1772
⊕ Localisation1(97)	1,2737	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2737	1,2237
⊕ Localisation1(98)	1,2993	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2993	1,2493
⊕ Localisation1(99)	1,3020	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,3020	1,2520
⊕ Localisation1(100)	1,2806	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2806	1,2306
⊕ Localisation1(101)	1,2585	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2585	1,2085
⊕ Localisation1(102)	1,2362	0,0000	0,0500	0,0000	1,2362	1,1862
— Rectitude axe cylindre	0,5177	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,5177	0,4177
— Rectitude Y-	0,1301	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,1301	0,0301
— Rectitude X-	0,5001	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,5001	0,4001
— Rectitude X+	0,4842	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,4842	0,3842
— Rectitude Y+	0,0350	0,0000	0,1000	0,0000	0,0350	

**CONSTRUCTION AND RF TESTS OF THE COMPACTLIGHT
ACCELERATING STRUCTURE PROTOTYPE**

Milestone: MS30

Date: 22/09/2025

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Nom

axe cylindre

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Norm
 axe Y-

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Nom

axe X+

EDMS 3317020
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